

**DELIVERABLE D4.5 – Mid-term
report on project
management**

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Main author	E. Skalická
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Abbreviations

- CA** – consortium agreement
- CFS** – Certificate on the financial statements
- CU** – Comenius University
- EU** – European Union
- FP** – Framework programme
- GA** – Grant agreement
- HE** – Horizon Europe
- HR** – Human resources
- KPIs** – Key performance indicators
- MSCA-PF** – Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellowship
- MUNI** – Masaryk University
- PM** – Project manager
- R&I** – Research and Innovation
- SC** – Steering Committee
- UWB** – University of West Bohemia in Pilsen
- WP** – Work package

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Executive summary

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the project consortium structure, including a brief summary of the work packages, as well as the platforms used for internal collaboration and reporting (both periodic and internal). It also outlines key points discussed during Steering Committee meetings. According to the Grant Agreement, the report will be updated at the end of the project.

Key words

Coordinator, deliverable, manager, meeting, milestone, reporting, Steering committee, Work package

1 Introduction

The COLOSSE project involves 6 participants – the Masaryk University as a coordinator, Comenius University and University of West Bohemia in Pilsen as beneficiaries and 3 associated partners (Linköpings Universitet, Montanuniversitaet Leoben and Rheinisch-Westfaelische Technische Hochschule Aachen). The project connects research facilities in the area of plasma-enabled surface engineering to increase their participation in Horizon Europe and future EU Framework Programmes for R&I.

Figure 1 COLOSSE participants

This report provides a brief overview of the project's internal management structure and coordination mechanisms. The document serves as a reference point for all consortium members, offering insight into how the project is managed on both strategic and operational levels.

The report includes a summary of the governance bodies. It also presents the internal platforms used for collaboration, documentation sharing, and reporting. Key points and recommendations from Steering Committee meetings are briefly highlighted.

This document is a living deliverable and will be updated at the end of the project, as specified in the Grant Agreement.

2 Project governance structure

The project management is based on a clear organizational structure, which includes a Steering Committee, a Coordinator, a Project Manager, and individual Work Package Leaders. This structure ensures efficient oversight, coordination, and implementation of all project activities.

The **Steering Committee** is the decision-making body of the consortium which consists of one representative of each Party and is chaired by project coordinator. Steering Committee meets at least once every six months and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member (agendas and key points from past meetings are in Annex 2).

Details of organizational structure, decisions, voting rules, veto rights etc. are described in Consortium agreement.

The **Coordinator** acts as an intermediary between the partners and the grant provider. In addition to its duties as a partner, the coordinator performs the tasks as collecting and reviewing the consistency of submitting reports and deliverables, preparing meetings etc. Details are listed in CA.

The **Project manager** (PM) is appointed by the coordinator. The PM is responsible for monitoring of the project (milestones, deliverables, resources used etc.), consolidating individual contributions to technical and financial reports and communicating with the European Commission. The PM ensures the smoothly running of the project and cooperates with Work package leaders to fulfil the tasks.

The **Work Package leaders** coordinate activities of dedicated Work package to ensure completion of project deliverables and milestones.

3 Work structure

The project is divided into 5 work packages (WP), each of them has dedicated agenda, but the activities are connected and build on each other.

WP1 – the aim is to deliver the COLOSSE Internationalization Strategy, reinforce links with strategic partners and to implement the R&I mobility scheme.

WP2 – the aim is to develop the COLOSSE Human Resources Development Strategy, establish pilot measures to practically verify measures for recruitment and on-boarding with a postdoctoral scheme and implement a training programme to boost skills of COLOSSE researchers.

WP3 – the aim is to present a structured pathway towards development of HE/FP project proposals, including development of competencies of researchers and research managers.

WP4 – the aim is to provide a governance framework for the whole project, ensure proper monitoring, reporting, and data management.

WP5 – the aim is to cover implementation of dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities.

Figure 2 Scheme of Work packages

Each work package consists of several tasks. The details about schedule of each work packages, their tasks and dedicated deliverables/milestones are listed in Gantt chart in GA.

4 Internal cooperation

4.1. Meetings

For internal communication, we primarily use Microsoft Teams for online meetings and daily collaboration (Zoom is also available as an alternative platform when needed). Whenever possible, we prefer to meet in person to support more effective interaction. All meetings (online or physical) are held with a clear agenda prepared in advance to ensure focused and productive discussions.

4.2. SharePoint

We use SharePoint for document sharing and collaboration, which allows easy access to all authorized persons. The advantage is version control and centralized storage of project-related materials.

For the sake of an effective collaboration, the whole team is requested to always upload all the documents to the SharePoint starting already with their early drafts version and use the online editing tools when working on all project documents. Each work package has its own folder, ensuring that materials are well organized and accessible. In addition, there are special folders for internal reporting, budget tracking, deliverables, and contracts. There is also a table with an overview of key dates, milestones, indicators, Gantt chart etc.

4.3. Templates

To ensure consistency in documentation, templates for deliverables, presentations, and meeting minutes are available to all partners. These templates help ensure a uniform format and quality for all project outputs.

4.4. Contacts

We have a shared contact list that includes the persons responsible for individual work packages for all project partners. In addition, each partner keeps its own internal list of relevant persons to be informed about upcoming activities.

5 Risk management

Masaryk University, as the Coordinator, plays a central role in preparing and monitoring the Table of Risks. However, all partners are expected to contribute to risk identification and updates to the Table of Risks.

The risks listed in Annex 1 will be regularly updated throughout the project's duration to ensure proper identification, analysis, control, and monitoring of risks.

6 Monitoring and reporting

As stated in the Grant Agreement, the beneficiaries must continuously report on the progress of the action (continuous reporting). In addition to this ongoing reporting, a Periodic Report must be submitted at the end of each reporting period, and a Final Report is required at the end of the project. We have two reporting periods, the first from M1 to M15 and the second from M16 to M36.

Both the Periodic and Final Reports consist of two main parts:

- a technical part, describing the progress, outcomes, and deliverables of the project, and
- a financial part, detailing the use of resources, the financial statements (individual and consolidated) and the certificates on the financial statements (CFS) (if required).

All reports will be prepared in accordance with the official templates provided on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal to ensure compliance with the required structure and content.

The internal reporting is also carried out throughout the project. This includes regular updates from all partners on the progress of their work packages, key performance indicators, financial expenditure, and any risks or deviations. Internal reports are used to monitor the implementation of the action, prepare official reports, and ensure smooth coordination between beneficiaries. The template for internal monitoring is available on the project SharePoint.

7 Useful documents

[AGA – Annotated Grant Agreement](#) – detailed and continuously updated document setting out the financial and implementation rules for grants, with a number of practical examples.

[FTO Online Manual](#) – provides a clear overview of the project preparation and implementation phases, contains interactive links between related chapters, and also links to relevant supporting documents

8 Annexes

8.1. Annex 1 – Table of Risks

Table of Risks								
Risk number	Work Package(s)	Description	Likelihood	Severity	Proposed mitigation measures	Did you apply the risk-mitigation measures?	Did the risk materialise?	Comments
1	WP1	Lack of willingness to collaborate on strategic level from leading institutions abroad.	low	high	We have involved three key partners as associated partners to demonstrate their commitment to the project. Their engagement will increase credibility of the consortium also for other external actors.			
2	WP1	Lack of willingness to host research visits from leading institutions abroad.	low	high	We are confident of the skills of our researchers and have selected a time-span for mobility that will enable them to meaningfully contribute to R&I at their host institutions.			
3	WP2	Low coherence of HR strategies on institutional level and of training and career development needs among COLOSSE centres.	low	medium	We are confident that we will be able to find strong connections because all the institutional HRS4R strategies have the same Charter & Code as their baseline.			
4	WP2	Low interest in postdoctoral positions at COLOSSE centres from researchers currently working abroad.	medium	medium	The COLOSSE centres already experienced international recruitment with ESF-funded mobility projects; we will share what worked to attract applicants and what did not in the consortium (including associated partners).			

5	WP2	Postdoctoral researchers leaving before the completion of their basic 18-month fellowship.	low	medium	While our upgrading aim specifically targets on-boarding that should prevent such situations, they cannot be fully prevented. In case the risk materializes, we will either propose extra recruitment for shorter term or resource reallocation.			
6	WP2	Low interest in training opportunities offered by COLOSSE.	low	medium	We have included research community of the COLOSSE centres as one of our key target groups for dissemination and tailored a communication strategy specifically for them.			
7	WP3	Failure to identify research topics of joint interest.	medium	medium	We will dedicate a full task to discussions on R&I priorities; we will be open to initiate work on priorities that are of mutual interest for two COLOSSE centres, or one where strategic partners could be easily involved, if we do not identify enough viable topics of interest to all the Widening partners of the consortium.			
8	WP3	Failure to identify suitable funding opportunities in HE/FP.	medium	medium	We will always keep track of opportunities that are not restricted by scientific disciplines, e.g. MSCA-DN, SE.			
9	WP3	Low interest of partners beyond the consortium to join project development with COLOSSE centres.	low	medium	We will seek to involve our strategic associated partners as the first choice; their reputation should increase credibility of our collaboration offers.			
10	WP4	Fluctuation on the position of project manager.	medium	low	MUNI as whole implements a significant number of HE projects, and thus either experienced managers could step in if needed, or newly recruited one can be easily trained by local experts.			

11	WP5	Failure the present a coherent technological offer in coordination of the COLOSSE centres.	low	high	MUNI has experience with advertisement of its infrastructure in national open access scheme; MUNI and UWB with Technology Centres for KETs; we will draw on these experiences as a baseline to develop a more complex COLOSSE technology inventory and collaboration offer.			
12	WP5	Low interest from international participants in the final dissemination workshop.	low	medium	We will advertise the workshop well in advance; and if we notice a low interest, we will broaden the target groups addressed (incl. e.g. regional industry).			

8.2. Annex 2 – Agendas and key points from SC meetings

8.2.1. 1st Steering Committee meeting (Kick-off meeting)

Date: April 4th–5th, 2024

Venue: Brno, Masaryk University, Faculty of Sciences

Agenda: Details in deliverable D4.4 Report from the kick-of meeting

8.2.2. 2nd Steering Committee meeting (M6 – HR Strategy)

Date: September 11th, 2024

Venue: Bratislava, Comenius University, Centre for Nanotechnology and Advanced Materials (CENAM)

Agenda: Overview of activities for each WPs, dedicated section on HR strategy

WPI Internationalization Strategy

- Plan for trips to strategic partners – Germany (Kiel, September), Sweden (Linköping, October), Belgium (Gent, December), template for joint presentation (about project, partners’ unique expertise and infrastructure, possible secondments)

- Strategy – call for sharing experiences from trips, 1st draft in January, discussion on proposed actions for strategy development, 2nd draft in February, comments till 10th March, finalization till 26th March

WP2 Human Resources Development Strategy

- mapping of COLOSSE areas in the checklist, used for strategy formulation, today mapping of competences
- discussion about trainings for project needs
- CDP – also with the link to the official Horizon Europe MSCA plan
- Finalisation of the strategy and submission at the end of September

WP3 Sustainability of ERDF Investment through Synergies

- 2nd training (Pilsen, 20th – 21st March 2025) – preliminary topic “call analysis and how to write the excellence section”
- Discussion on abstracts for follow-up projects (3 to be submitted) – each institution will coordinate the preparation of one abstract/proposal

WP4 Project Management

- Deliverables to be submitted 09/2024 - HR Strategy, DMP, DECP
- Next SC meeting – Pilsen, 19th March 2025, together with training on 20th – 21st March 2025
- 10/2024 –the first internal report for completion

WP5 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

- Project website, design manual
- Social networks – LinkedIn (main channel), Facebook and Instagram also available, if needed (rather use existing accounts)
- DECP – next call 17th September
- Post and article about event held in Bratislava
- Leaflet about postdoc positions on LinkedIn

Presentation from the 2nd SC meeting

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COLOSSE
Central European Platform for Plasma-Enabled Surface Engineering

COLOSSE consortium meeting

11th September, 2024
Bratislava

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Agenda

- 12:30 – 13:20 Lunch
- 13:30 – 13:45 Welcome and Tour the table
- 13:45 – 16:45 Agenda: WPs progress (coffee break at 15:00)
- 18:30 Dinner

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WPI Internationalization Strategy

- Task 1.1 Internationalization Strategy design (M1-M12)
 - Discussion of R&I priorities among partners.
 - Identification of key topics in the field of plasma-enabled surface engineering.
 - Identification of suitable strategic partners for mutual cooperation in the field of plasma physics and solid state physics.
 - First contact with selected associated academic partners (e-mails, calls...)
 - Planning business trips to associated partners
 - September 2024 Kiel University in Germany (UWB)
 - October 2024 University in Uppsala and Linköping University in Sweden (MUNI, CU, UWB)
 - December 2024 Ghent University in Belgium (MUNI, CU, UWB)
- Task 1.2 R&I mobility to establish links with strategic partners (M13-M36)

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WP2 HR Development Strategy

- Mapping of HR practices at individual partners conducted, see HR Checklist
- COLOSSE Leaflet for Recruitment Heads Up prepared and agreed by partners, see link here
- COLOSSE Recruitment and Onboarding Strategy designed and agreed by partners, see link here
- COLOSSE HR Strategy completed by adding a draft Training Strategy into the document with the COLOSSE Recruitment and Onboarding Strategy, see link here
- Discussion on the draft COLOSSE Training Strategy and a joint mapping of required competences for designing the training concept is planned for the Bratislava COLOSSE Consortium Meeting on September 11, 2024

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WP2 HR Development Strategy

- List of COLOSSE HR Strategy templates:
 - Attachment 1: COLOSSE Job Advertising Template
 - Attachment 2: The European Competency Framework for Researchers
 - Attachment 3: COLOSSE Key Competencies Template
 - Attachment 4: COLOSSE Training Need Questionnaire Survey Template
 - Attachment 5: COLOSSE Training Topics Template
 - Attachment 6: COLOSSE Career Development Plan Template
 - Attachment 7: COLOSSE Training Feedback Form
- COLOSSE Training Strategy Scheme:

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      A[IDENTIFICATION OF KEY COMPETENCIES] --> B[ASSESSING CORE TRAINING NEEDS]
      B --> C[SPECIFYING TRAINING TOPICS]
      C --> D[PREPARING CAREER DEVELOPMENT PLANS]
      D --> E[STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION]
      E --> F[EVALUATING QUALITY OF THE TRAINING]
      
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- Attachment 1: COLOSSE Key Competencies Template
- Attachment 4: COLOSSE Training Need Questionnaire Survey Template
- Attachment type 1: R1-2
- Attachment type 2: Support Staff
- Attachment 5: COLOSSE Career Development Plan Template
- Delivering training as an addition of the COLOSSE Work Package 3
- Attachment 6: COLOSSE Training Feedback Form

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WP3 Sustainability of ERDF Investment through Synergies

- Task 3.1 Training grant writing skills
 - CU: RMAs Training Impact* 12 – 13. 9. 2024
 - UWB: April 2025 (topic to be decided)
- Task 3.2 Formulation of COLOSSE R&I priorities
 - M18: determination of joint R&I directions
 - Ongoing plans for visits to associated strategic partners in 2024 (Kiel, Linköping, Uppsala, Gent...)
 - University of Leoben – connection already well established
 - M24: funding opportunities and engagement of international partners
 - Training of administration (EU projects oriented staff)
 - ? Online meetings (Colosse partners + identified suitable international partners)

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WP3 Sustainability of ERDF Investment through Synergies

- Task 3.3 Identification of funding opportunities
 - List of suitable framework programs and expected calls
 - Identification and setting-up of possible projects proposal timeline
- Task 3.4 Development of follow-up projects
 - Preparation of abstract / annotations of several projects including involvement of international partners
 - ? Every institution is leading at least one of them?

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WP4 Project management

- Task 4.1 Project governance (M1-M36)
 - Next Steering committee meeting – March 2025 (M12) – UWB (+ T3.1 training grant writing skills + T2.3 training scheme soft skills?)
- Task 4.2 Monitoring, reporting, evaluation (M1-M36)
 - SharePoint – contacts, overview etc.
 - Internal reporting
 - Deliverables and milestones in M6
- Task 4.3 Data management (M1-M36)
 - 1st draft of Data management plan

8.2.3.3rd Steering Committee meeting (M12 – Internationalization Strategy)

Date: March 20th, 2025

Venue: Pilsen, University of West Bohemia, Faculty of Applied Sciences

Agenda: Overview of activities for each WPs, dedicated section on Internationalization strategy

WP1 Internationalization Strategy

- Draft of deliverable discussed, will be submitted next week
- possibility of the online meeting with sister projects from Pathways to Synergies call (discussion about Internationalization strategies) – 24th March 2025 at 11 a.m.

WP2 Human Resources Development Strategy

- training request for postdocs regarding the upcoming MSCA-PF call (MUNI will check the availability of internal trainer)
- T2.3 soft skills training – 1st training at MUNI (28th – 29th April 2025) – topic “AI”
- 1st Retreat (CU) – 09/2025 (Modra), shared table with participants

WP3 Sustainability of ERDF Investment through Synergies

- Discussion on call monitoring, creation of an overview of current and future calls (e.g. regular announcements) – shared table, ongoing updates
- Drafts for follow-up projects – ideal 1-2 institutions from COLOSSE + 1 foreign partner as a core group for the project plan, then inviting other partners with already formulated concrete ideas

WP4 Project Management

- Deliverables to be submitted by 03/2025 – ideally by 28/03
- Deliverables to be submitted by 06/2025
 - o D2.2. Report on international recruitment
 - o D4.2. DMP v2
 - o D4.5. Mid-term report on project management
 - o D5.3. DECP v2
- Next SC meeting – 09/2025, together with Retreat or online
- Reporting (RPI – M1 – M15) – shared template, 1st draft in June
- Review – 3rd September (agreed)

WP5 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

- D5.2 Technology offer – discussion on draft, adding links to partners' websites, submission next week
- discussion on the best way how to promote it

Presentation from the 3rd SC meeting

COLOSSE consortium meeting
20th March, 2025
Plzeň

Agenda

- 15:30 – 15:45 Welcome and Tour the table
- 15:45 – 17:00 WPs progress
- 18:30 Dinner

WPI Internationalization Strategy

- Task 1.1 Internationalization Strategy design (M1-M12)
 - Discussion of R&I priorities among partners.
 - * Identification of key topics in the field of plasma-enabled surface engineering.
 - * Identification of suitable strategic partners for mutual cooperation in the field of plasma physics and solid state physics.
 - First contact with selected associated academic partners (e-mails, calls...)
 - Planning business trips to associated partners
 - * September 2024 Kiel University in Germany (UWB)
 - * October 2024 University in Uppsala and Linköping University in Sweden (MUN, CU, UWB)
 - * December 2024 Mons University & Ghent in Belgium (MUN, UWB)
 - * January 2025 RWTH Aachen in Germany (CU, UWB, MUN)
- Task 1.2 R&I mobility to establish links with strategic partners (M13-M36)
 - * April 2025 RWTH Aachen – 1 person from CU

WP2 HR Development Strategy

- Task 2.1 HR Strategy design (M1-M6)
 - Deliverable submitted
- Task 2.2 Pilot international recruitment and career development strategy for young researchers (M4-M36)
 - Joint call opened in October 2024
 - Selection procedure
 - On-boarding of new postdocs (CDP in 1st month, MSCA-PF)
 - * CU – 2nd postdocs will start in May 2025
 - * MUNI – 1st postdoc will start in October 2025, new call for the second position
 - * UWB – 1st postdoc will start in March 2025, 2nd postdoc in October 2025

WP2 HR Development Strategy

- Task 2.3 COLOSSE training scheme (M7-M36)
 - Preparation of 1st training (MUN) – topic: Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools
 - Possible dates: 28th-29th April, 5th-6th May

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WP2 HR Development Strategy

Soft and transferrable skills

Skill	Researcher (M1-M2)	Manager / Administrator	Leaving project collaborator
Adaptability & Flexibility	15	10	5
School and Social Responsibility	10	10	10
Working with Scientific Results and Resources	15	15	15
Time Management	17	17	17
Use of Research Methods & Techniques	18	18	18
Problem Solving & Critical Thinking	18	18	18
Teamwork & Collaboration	18	18	18
Knowledge of Open Access, Open Science, etc.	19	19	19
Proficiency in English or another language	21	21	21
Communication Skills	24	24	24
Managing Work-Life Balance	27	27	27
Leadership & Management	30	30	30
Managing Difficult Situations	31	31	31
Understanding of Financial Project Management	32	32	32
Research Project Management and Administration	33	33	33
Scientific Writing and Publication	35	35	35
Research Project Management	35	35	35
Use of Artificial Intelligence Tools	39	39	39
Identification of Funding Opportunities for Research	41	41	41

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WP3 Sustainability of ERDF Investment through Synergies

- Task 3.1 Training grant writing skills
 - CU-RMAs Training „Impact“ 12. – 13. 9. 2024
 - UWB, RMAs Training „Scientific excellence in project proposals: concept, methods, and tools“ 20.-21.3.2025
- Task 3.2 Formulation of COLOSSE R&I priorities
 - MIR: determination of joint R&I directions
 - Visits to associated strategic and other partners in 2024/25 (Kiel, Linköping, Uppsala, Mons, Gent, Aachen), University of Leoben – connection already well established
 - Identification of areas of common interest – written reports
 - M24: funding opportunities and engagement of international partners
 - Training of administration (EU projects oriented staff)
 - Analysis of drafts of expected calls
 - Online meetings (Colosse partners + identified suitable international partners)

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WP3 Sustainability of ERDF Investment through Synergies

- Task 3.3 Identification of funding opportunities
 - List of suitable framework programs and expected calls (based on analysis done in 2025/26?)
 - Identification and setting-up of a possible projects proposal timeline (general or concrete?, definition of each step, definition of responsibilities)
- Task 3.4 Development of follow-up projects
 - Preparation of abstract / annotations of several project proposals including involvement of international partners
 - Every institution is responsible for the preparation (leadership) of at least one of them

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WP4 Project management

- Task 4.1 Project governance (M1-M36)
 - Next Steering committee meeting – September 2025 (M18) – CU (+Retreat?) – topic „R&I priorities“
- Task 4.2 Monitoring, reporting, evaluation (M1-M36)
 - SharePoint – contacts, overview update
 - Deliverables and milestones in M12 – D11 (MS3), D5.2 (MS4)
 - Deliverables in M15 – D2.2 (Report on international recruitment, D4.2 (DMP V2), D4.5 (Mid-term report on project management), D5.3 (DECP V2)
 - 1st Periodic report (M1-M15) – next slide
- Task 4.3 Data management (M1-M36)
 - Update in M15

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WP4 Project management

- 1st Periodic report (M1-M15)
 - all data reported in Continuous Reporting will be automatically included in the Periodic Reporting
 - partners will receive notification to log in to the Portal to complete the report
 - MUNI must submit report within 60 days following the end of RPI (by 29th at the latest)
 - technical and financial part
 - Review meeting
 - after submission of report
 - PO and external expert
 - Online
 - 3rd September 2025

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WP5 Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication

- Task 5.1 Design of Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan (M1-M6)
 - Identification of communication channels to target groups (academic partners, industry, public).
 - Creation of the **colosse.eu** website and the design of the manual for public presentation and official documents.
 - Creation of a COLOSSE account on social networks LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram.
- Task 5.2 Implementation of Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Plan (M1-M36) – posts on LinkedIn, website update
- Task 5.3 COLOSSE Technology Offer (M7-M12) – deliverable will be submitted next week, discussion on how to promote it

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Thank you!

Questions?

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